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INFLATION IN INDIA: A LITERATURE REVIEW

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Abstract:

Rising inflation is a concern for all the countries. Since independence India has been facing inflationary pressure. Several factors have worked behind inflation in India. Both structural and monetary causes have contributed to the inflation in India. The paper is an attempt to review the available literature on inflation in India. It studies different aspects of inflation in India in a structured manner. The paper reviews the causes of persistent inflation in India, how core inflation can contribute in the determination of headline inflation in India and the trends of inflation in India. The study explores the role of policy regimes in controlling inflation. Based on recommendations of various economists it is propounded that 2 per cent to 4 per cent inflation may be considered good for any economy. As on one side it reduces the risk of hitting zero bound and on other side it ensures the growth of the economy. Till date in India inflation targeting has never been adopted rigorously but now central bank has taken a target to reduce the inflation in India and policies are being designed to eradicate inflation from Indian economy.

Key Words: Inflation, Core Inflation, Wholesale Price Index (WPI), Consumer Price Index(CPI), Headline Inflation.

Introduction:

Inflation is defined as a percentage increase in the general price level of prices of goods and services in an economy over a period of time. Due to rise in the general price level, each unit of currency buys fewer goods and services i.e. purchasing power of money falls. Thus, inflation results in loss of value of money. A raise and tumble in the monetary value of a particular good or service cannot be termed as inflation. Change in individual prices reflects changes in choice and preferences of consumers and/or to changing costs. Inflation occurs

when most prices, are rising by some degree across the whole economy. Inflation is the outcome of imbalance between the forces of demand and supply. The imbalance may exist for demand and supply of money and/or for demand and supply of goods and services. The nascence of inflation is attributed to increase in supply of money compared to its demand and/or increase in demand for goods and services, compared to their supply. Inflation may be classified on the basis of coverage and scope, time of occurrence, government reaction, rising prices, driving forces and expectations of people.

Figure: 1.1 Classification of Inflation

1.1 Demand-Pull Inflation:

Root of 'Demand-Pull Inflation' lies in the increase in the aggregate demand of households, commercial enterprises, governments and foreign purchasers. When the concurrent demand of these four sectors exceeds the output, the economy can produce then these sectors compete to purchase limited amount of goods and services Buyers in essence "bid prices up", which again causes inflation. Many forces work behind aggregate demand in an economic system. In an expanding economy, factors like deficit financing, increase in credit by federal bank, increase in foreign trade, increase in population and fast growth of other economies, increased government spending, reduction in direct taxes and the growth of the money supply, all account for increase in the aggregate demand. At a given point of time when aggregate demand exceeds aggregate supply and supply cannot be increased beyond a level, then the price level starts portraying upward trend.

According to Monetarists, led by Milton Friedman, excess demand is the direct result of increase in the stock of money. It is the growth in the supply of money that is solely responsible for inflation (i.e. growth in price level) in the economy. The Keynesians, on the other hand, deny the direct influence of growth in the supply of money on inflation and argue that it is not the money supply, but the money expenditure that influences the price level. According to followers of Keynes, "money supply is one of the many factors that exert influence over price level".

1.2 Cost Push Inflation:

Cost-Push (Supply-side) Inflation finds its way into the growing cost of production of goods and services. Cost push inflation may be imputed to rise in the prices of oil, higher indirect taxes and higher import prices and higher cost of production. e.g. If the wages of workers are raised without an increase in the productivity then, the unit cost of production also increases. This results into increase in the prices of end-products or end-services being produced and supplied.

Supporters of cost push theories (also called sellers’ or mark-up theories) of inflation, state that cause of inflation is the autonomous increases in the important components of cost of production. These theories attribute the phenomenon of inflation to the increase in the wages, profits and material prices, all of whom constitute the cost of production. The increase in the cost of production is passed on to the customers in the form of higher prices leading to inflation.

1.3 Inflation Cycle:

An increase in the general price level is the cause of concern for every country. Persistent inflation is not considered conducive for the growth of any economy. To keep inflation under control is one of the key targets of every central bank. Inflation cycle is very complicated and it is very difficult to break the vicious circle of inflation. Inflation itself is a cause of expectation of increase in the general price level and the effect of such an expectation is increased inflation in future. To keep inflation under control, the central bank and the

Figure 1.2 Inflation Cycle

government of any country design policies viz. Monetary and Fiscal. The central bank through changes in interest rates and through ‘Open Market Operations (OMO)’ tries to reduce excessive money supply from the market. Interest rate hike is one of the tool used by central bank to absorb excessive money supply from the market. Although increased interest rates lead to reduction in excessive demand and help increasing savings but persistent high interest rates put up a pressure on cost of production.

Increase in interest rates leads to increased cost of production, which further leads to the expectation of increase in the general price level, due to anticipation of increase in the inflation in future, present consumption increases, which leads to the expansion of credit, contraction of domestic savings and expansion of monetized debt which ultimately leads to increase in inflation. If the government fails to keep the fiscal deficit under control then the central bank alone can’t meet its target to control inflation. Fiscal deficit supported by increased money supply through issuance of new currency notes becomes one of the cause of depreciation of currency. Depreciation of currency is nothing but decrease in the external purchasing power of money. It makes imports costlier. Depreciation of currency proves detrimental for a country like India who meets nearly 80 per cent of its demand for crude oil through imports (Business Standard, 2013). Increased cost of imports particularly that of

crude oil adds to food price inflation as well as increases the cost of production. Average consumer price inflation in India in past 30 years has broadly ranged from 9 per cent to 12 per cent. During this period average CPI inflation touched a peak of 13.88 per cent in 1991 and witnessed a low of 3.77 per cent in 2001 and 2004. with a very few years as an exception when the average inflation rate fell below 8 per cent (Ministry of Statistics and Program Implementation).

A number of economists feel that a double digit inflation may be damaging to the wellness of an economic system, but a four per cent inflation target may be considered secure for any economy (Blanchard et al. 2010). 2-4 per cent of inflation may be considered secure for any economy. It indicates that the economy is growing. Economists have made several arguments for raising inflation targets above two per cent. However, one argument stands out as compelling: a higher target would reduce the risk that interest rates hit zero. Yet, the idea has been widely unpopular among monetary economists, and it is anathema to central bankers. According to (Bernanke 2010a), the Federal Open Market Committee unanimously opposes an increase in its inflation goal, which “would likely entail, much greater costs than benefits”.

2.0. Literature Review:

Inflation has been a burning issue in almost all the countries of the world. Now a days, most of the countries are devising their policies to target inflation. Considering the inflation and the issues related with it, this study will consider different aspects of inflation viz. trends of inflation in India, causes of inflation in India, role of core inflation in determination of headline inflation, forecasts of inflation in India and effectiveness of policy regimes in targeting inflation. Considering varied aspects of inflation review of literature has been segregated accordingly.

2.1 Inflation trends:

India has been facing inflationary trends since independence. Inflation in India is attributed to government policy of deficit financing. The government has followed aggressively the policy of deficit financing to meet its growth target. Through deficit financing spending of government increase and it helps creating employment opportunities but at the same time it builds inflationary wave in the economy. Inflation in India was quite low in 1950s, In 1960s India crossed double digit inflation same was attributed to war with China. 1970s witnessed high inflation, which was more than 20 per cent. During 1980s the inflation cooled down and it started rising again in 1990s.

According to Batura (2008) WPI inflation in India in 2007 increased to 6 per cent which was higher than the forecasts made by RBI. Increase in inflation was attributed to increase in prices of oil. Deaton (2008) says that food price inflation has risen sharply in India. But the research also highlights the need for review of indices. Outdated indices may be one of the cause of apparent higher inflation. Food price inflation in India has shown a higher side trend as compared to headline inflation Bhandari and Majumda, 2011 (The Hindu Businessline). India has witnessed inflationary trend but in India food price inflation and oil price inflation have generally been higher than headline inflation.

2.2 Core Inflation as an estimator of Headline Inflation:

The more familiar core inflation measures as aggregate price growth excluding food and energy appears to have first been analysed in a systematic fashion in 1975 by Gordon R. Thereafter Eckstein (1981) in a book ‘Core Inflation’ used the term core inflation for the first time. Eckstein defines core inflation as “The trend increase in the cost of the factors of production. It originates in the long-term expectations of inflation in the minds of households and businesses, in the contractual arrangements which sustain the wage-price momentum and in the tax system”. In the book consideration has been given to a Phillips curve augmented by inflation expectations and supply shocks. Core rate is strongly

influenced by inflationary expectations. These expectations are part and responses to the past history of inflation.

Although unanimity is not found amongst the economists on the definition of core inflation but almost all agree about the importance of core inflation in the measurement of headline inflation. Bryan and Cecchetti (1994) define core inflation as the measure most correlated with money growth whereas Bryan et al. (1997) define it as the measure most correlated with a smoothed trend inflation rate. Smith (2004) says that core inflation is the best forecaster of inflation. Mishkin (2007) has given a very clear definition of core inflation. According to Mishkin, "Measures of core inflation attempt to strip out or smooth volatile changes in particular prices to distinguish the inflation signal from the transitory noise". Thus, relative to changes in headline inflation measures, changes in core measures are much less likely to be reversed, provide a clearer picture of the underlying inflation pressures, and so serve as a better guide to where headline inflation itself is heading.

Recent developments and the interest in core inflation reflects its usefulness as a tool for policy. A measure of core inflation could be both a better guide for current and future policy than published inflation rates and a measure of inflation that is more controllable. There are two basic approaches to measuring core inflation. One the statistical approach and the other the modelling approach. The statistical approach is a practical, data-driven approach Hogen et al. (2001). Brayan and Cecchetti (1994), Mohanty et al. (2000), Smith (2001) and Rich R. (2007), all admit the importance of limited influence indicators in measurement of core inflation. These limited influence indicators can be Trimmed Mean, Weighted Median. Decision as to percentage of trimming of observations on each side depends upon index used. Meyler (1999), Clark (2001) and Bermingham (2007) compare forecast errors from an ARIMA model and a simple regression respectively. Whereas Quah and Vahey (1995) and Rich R. (2007), support the use of time series and structured VAR model.

In the Indian context also, the properties of core inflation measures have been tested by some researchers Samanta (1999), Mohanty et al (2000) and Das et al. (2009). Samanta (1999) computed core inflation following the exclusion principle, Mohanty et al. (2000) made a comprehensive attempt to examine core inflation measures i.e. trimmed mean, weighted median and exclusion based measures.

2.3 Structural and Monetary causes of Inflation:

The followers of monetarist school argue that money is all that matters in explaining inflation. According to monetarist "inflation is always and everywhere a monetary phenomenon". Whereas the structuralist school, argues that structural and institutional factors play a more prominent role in inflation dynamics. According to them inelastic food supply, infrastructural inadequacies that pose problems for distribution of output, lack of financial resources and low export receipts leading to foreign exchange shortages in developing countries put pressure on domestic prices London (1989). The debate between monetarists and structuralists makes it hard to determine what actually causes inflation. Friedman (1968) says that transitory movements in the measured rate of inflation can be driven by shocks of various kinds, but large and persistent movements in inflation cannot occur without the help of monetary policy. Friedman's view was considered to be controversial at times but in present day it provides base to various studies. Blinder (1982), Hetzel (1998), and Mayer (1998) all attribute the upward secular trend in inflation to a systematic tendency for Federal Reserve policy to translate the short-run price pressures set off by adverse supply shocks into more persistent changes in the inflation rate.

2.4 Role of policy regimes in targeting inflation:

There exists a number of studies about the success of inflation targeting. Examining the performance in countries like New Zealand, Canada, UK and Germany, Mishkin and Posen

(1997) have observed that inflation targeting has been successful in enabling them maintain low level of inflation that they were not able to do in the past. To adopt the inflation-targeting framework there are certain prerequisites and technical issues as indicated in Blejer and Leone (2000). One must have clear understanding of the monetary policy transmission mechanism and reliable forecasts of inflation. This shows that setting appropriate inflation targets require not only accurate forecast but also knowledge of the channels through which policy variables affect inflation. In context of monetary policy instrument rules and target rules may be used to target inflation Rudebusch (1999). Walsh (2009), in the study with 26 industrialized countries, has observed that while among developed countries, inflation targeting has led to similar macroeconomic experience to non-inflation targeting, it led to improved macroeconomic performance among developing economies. Whereas Subbarao (2009) points out that "... inflation-targeting is neither desirable nor practical in India for a number of reasons." These include (a) the need of a central bank of a developing country being guided by price stability, financial stability and growth; (b) food items continue to be vulnerable to supply shocks, especially because of vagaries of monsoon, and are beyond the ambit of monetary policy; (c) inefficient transmission mechanism due to large fiscal deficits, presence of administered prices and interest rates and illiquid private bond market; and (d) managing volatility of exchange rate in the face of disorderly capital flows. Urjit Committee (2014), made several important recommendations related to the conduct of monetary policy in India. These include (a) Using the Consumer Price Index (CPI) inflation as the nominal anchor for monetary policy communication; (b) moving towards a flexible inflation-targeting regime over the next two years with a target of 4% within a band of $\pm 2\%$; and (c) setting up a five member Monetary Policy Committee, which will be responsible for making policy decisions, and be held accountable in case of failure to meet the nominal target. Nachane (2014) argues that inflation targeting regime, with a desire to manage inflation, could have an adverse effect on a number of macro financial variables including exchange rate management, fiscal policy and financial stability.

Conclusion:

Since long inflation in India has been on higher side. Inflation in India may be attributed to long period of deficit financing since independence and to the oil price inflation. India procures nearly 80 per cent of its demand for oil through import. Thus increase in oil prices leads to increase in inflation in India. Further government and central bank of India failed to control the inflation in India. Generally 2 to 4 per cent of inflation is considered good for the growth of any economy but in India inflation has generally ranged from 6 per cent to 8 per cent. Whereas food inflation has been even higher. In India inflation is measured by Wholesale Price Index (WPI) whereas most of the countries in the world have abandoned WPI and have shifted to CPI. CPI is considered a better measure of inflation. It tells about the burden of increased price level on ultimate consumer. But in 2014 acting on the Urjit committee report India has decided to move from WPI to CPI. Further in India it seems that core inflation has a little scope. As, in India more than 50 per cent of the inflation is attributed to food and oil price inflation. Whereas core inflation excludes food and energy inflation due to their highly volatile nature. But still core inflation measures the persistent part of inflation. Thus its importance in policy formulation can't be ignored. In this regard suggestion of Urjit committee to follow the gliding path to target inflation seems quite logical.

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